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AN ANALYSIS OF CIVIC EDUCATION AS A COMPULSORY COURSE TO BUILD THE NATIONAL CHARACTER OF INDONESIA

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to determine the role and constraints of civic education as a compulsory subject in tertiary education to build Indonesia's national character of Indonesia. This study used a qualitative approach with library research methods. The data collection technique employed document studies using the data sources from books, previous research reports, journal articles, proceedings, online news and the like as the data sources. The data analysis used inductive analysis. The study results showed that civic education as a compulsory subject in higher education builds civic knowledge, skills, and disposition. Theoretically, this course is crucial for building students' national character, in fact, the application is still far from expectations. The goals of building national character are not optimally achieved. It can be seen from the students' behaviour and personality as the digital native generations, which do not reflect Pancasila's national character, such as disobeying the law and misusing drugs. Civic education has several obstacles due to the lack of teaching hours (only two credits) and the low lecturers' competencies. Moreover, the students are more interested in foreign cultures than local ones. The online learning condition also decreases students' learning motivation.

KEYWORDS

Civic education; Compulsory Courses; National Character.

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INTRODUCTION

Since the development of human resources is a continuous process, any country must set education as a top priority. Every country works hard to establish a high-level educational system to provide its people with a quality and humane learning process. As the world's fourth most populous country, Indonesia is trying hard to develop educational quality as one of the national goals listed in the Preamble of the 1945 Constitution, i.e., educating national life. This is also reinforced by the enactment of Law Number 20 of 2003 concerning the National Education System. The regulation explains that the function of national education is to shape the students 'character. It indicates that character education is a significant element in building human resources. In creating the nation's character, civic education plays a crucial part. The regulation, specifically in Article 37, requires elementary and tertiary civic education. Law Number 12 of 2012 concerning Higher Education in Article 35 also explains that civic education is a compulsory course for higher education. Some of these rules show the importance of Civic Education as a foundation for developing national character for students(Widiatmaka, 2021).

Creating citizens who are intelligent, democratic, active, and critical while still committed to upholding unity and oneness as well as national integrity is one of the goals of citizenship education as a tool for developing national character. Other goals include creating a civilised democratic culture and developing citizens with quality citizenship skills.(Ubaidillah & Razaq, 2009). Civic education primarily aims to mold students into good and intelligent citizens in the hopes that each student will possess a number of indicators as a good and intelligent citizen, including possessing the information, abilities, and citizenship attitudes, among which is having self-confidence (civic confidence), skills (civic competency), and dedication (civic commitment)(Winarno, 2019). Yet, when we observe the phenomenon occurring in Indonesia, we see that while many students have taken civic education courses, many of their activities do not align with the nation's values, even though some have crossed the law.

Data from the Indonesian Institute of Sciences (LIPI) consistent with the State Intelligence Agency (BIN) result shows that 39% of Indonesian students from various tertiary institutions among 15 provinces are exposed to radicalism.(Ruhyani, 2018). Several North Sumatra University students organised drug parties, which was illegal. The National Narcotics Agency of North Sumatra Province detained 47 students on suspicion of drug use, but after an investigation, it was determined that 31 of them had used drugs. The remaining 16 students were released because they tested negative for drugs. (Rahmawati, 2021). Sexual harassment or sexual violence is a very unpleasant occurrence that has taken place in several Indonesian colleges, according to the findings of a survey by the Ministry of Education, Culture, Research and Technology in 2020, which included responses from 79 tertiary institutions in 29 cities throughout Indonesia, 77% of respondents, reported that sexual violence had occurred in universities. Additionally, 63% of sexual harassment cases were not reported to those in charge of upholding the university's reputation, and 90% of victims of sexual harassment were women. (Sucahyo, 2022).

The objectives of national education to build a strong nation's character and produce citizens who are pious and responsible have not been adequately attained. The phenomenon of harmful student activities is a portrait of education in Indonesia. Also, considering that many student behaviours directly conflict with the nation's principles (Pancasila values), the role of civic education as a required course in higher institutions has not yielded maximum outcomes. In contrast, Cipto asserts

that the goal of civics education in tertiary institutions is to prepare students to become godly, democratic, and civilised citizens(Hamidah, 2019).

Muhajir and Sugiarti carried out previous research in 2019 on the analysis of the Pancasila and Civic Education learning implementation in forming students' character at Muhammadiyah 1 Makassar Middle School, showing that the performance of Civics learning has tried to instil character values, but the results are still not ideal. This may occur due to the shortage of learning hours, pupils' lack of awareness of the value of character, and their theoretical lack of understanding of its importance(Muhajir & Sugiarti, 2019).This study demonstrates that civics education should be enhanced in postsecondary institutions and secondary education. The implementation of defending the state in the technological era in civic education was also the subject of subsequent research by Ahyati and Dewi in 2021. The research findings indicate that the role of citizenship education in the technological era needs to be increased because the challenges are becoming more dynamic(Ahyati & Dewi, 2021). The findings of this study also highlight that civic education still plays a subpar role in the educational process, which limits the growth of national character. Therefore, the main goals of this study are to assess how civics education contributes to the development of national character and to identify how civics education is used in universities to accomplish these goals.

RESEARCH METHOD

This study uses a qualitative approach with library research methods because the data collected uses document studies regarding the analysis of civics education implementation as a compulsory subject among tertiary institutions in building the national character of Indonesia. Mirshad explained that the steps in library research are searching for literature and sources related to the research problem being studied, then elaborating the data (theory with new findings), analysis, criticism, and ideas related to the data found, especially previous studies to presenting new findings (Sari & Asmendri, 2020). The data collection technique in this study was document study from books, journal articles, previous research, proceedings, online news, magazines, and other information from social media.

Based on Mirshad's opinion, the research stages include 1) a literature review related to the implementation of civics education as a compulsory course in tertiary institutions in Indonesia form of books, journal articles, proceedings, research reports, online news, magazines and magazines and so on. 2) data elaboration through document studies, especially previous studies and theories on the role of education and the constraints of civic in building national character,3) data analysis through document studies to produce related analysis on the implementation of education in tertiary institutions, and 4) criticism and new ideas based on the analysis results of the civics implementation as a compulsory course in tertiary institutions. The data analysis used in this study is inductive analysis because it examines the theoretical foundation of the role of civics education in building the nation's character in tertiary institutions to produce a conclusion that will serve as the basis for providing recommendation.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The Role of Civic Education in Building National Character

Civic education viewed from a pedagogical aspect is a field of curricular programs and multidimensional socio-cultural activities, so it is considered as political education, democracy domain, legal education, anti-corruption insight, values, moral building and so on(Murtiningsih et al., 2022). Citizenship education is a learning plan that seeks to humanise humans, cultivate and empower

citizens, especially students to become good and intelligent citizens based on applicable laws and regulations. (Asyari & Dewi, 2021). Civic education in tertiary institutions is a learning process that utilises various methods and learning media to shape students' character and intelligence. It is considered as the core aspect for Indonesian education in shaping the nation's character (Widiatmaka & Purwoko, 2021). Citizenship education is the main basis in developing the attitudes and behavior of a person based on the nation character (Aksinudin et al., 2022). According to Branson, civic education basically seeks to form three competencies among students, namely civic knowledge, which emphasises aspects of civic knowledge; civic skills emphasising civic abilities, and civic disposition that is related to personality or civic character. Theoretically, this course has a strategic role to build the people's morals and character, especially students (Nuryadi & Widiatmaka, 2022).

Citizenship education is the leading sector of character education, especially in building the nation's personality (Insani et al., 2021). Civic education is essential in shaping the nation's character and national identity. This course aims to educate citizens to become good and intelligent people in facing the challenges of the current era. Character education integrated with civics will be beneficial for revitalising the role of civics education as a superior discipline for fostering national character. (Zulfikar & Dewi, 2021). National character is one of the abstract elements of national strength so that national character must be maintained and instilled in young generations as the nation's future. This greatly affects the nation's resilience, preservation and cultivation through education. Undeniably, citizenship education is the spearhead for building national character among the younger generation. (Anwar & Salim, 2019). The development of national character is so crucial that it relates to improving, fostering, and passing on citizens about the concepts, behaviors and noble values of the Indonesian nation's culture based on Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution. It is to shape the nation into an individual who is obedient, competitive, tough, tolerant, nationalist, patriotic, collaborative, dynamic and highly adaptive to changing times based on faith and piety to God Almighty (Yunus, 2013).

The teachers of civics education courses play a very important role, considering that educators are the key to success in building the nation's character, so they must have pedagogical, professional, personal and social competence. (Casma et al., 2022). In addition, the role of educators, especially in this case, is that lecturers have an important role in shaping students' character through civics education. Djamarah explained that a teacher during the learning process must be an inspiration, information source, organiser, motivator, initiator, , a mentor, classroom manager, mediator, demonstrator, corrector, supervisor, and evaluator (Sudirman, 2021). Another important thing is a teachers who is able to adapt to the times, especially technology and information, because the current students are digital native generations. Their daily life depends on the internet with all their interaction through their smartphone. Based on this phenomenon, many say that students in schools or colleges are digital beings (Kirschner & De Bruyckere, 2017).

Certain competencies must be met for students to succeed in civics education courses and have positive characters. These competencies include accepting all societal differences, being able to collaborate with any groups of people, and respecting and upholding every citizen's similar rights. Individual differences must be put aside in determining a certain position of an official government. People should maintain the respect for human rights in the national and state life (Zuriah, 2020). The goal of civic education in tertiary institutions is to create positive, intelligent students who can adapt to the times. Efforts have been made to maximise this course's function as a means of developing national character. Yet, the results reveal that this role falls short of expectations.

Obstacles to Civic Education in Building National Character

Triling explains that the challenges of the 21st-century learning are the low graduates' competencies from formal education, especially tertiary institutions. Those are related to verbal and written communication, critical thinking, problem-solving skills, professionalism and work ethics, collaboration skill, technology literacy, respect for equality, leadership and project management (Daryanto & Karim, 2017). Obstacles to citizenship education as a required subject in developing student character might range from a focus on cognitive elements to subpar lecturers' competency. This assessment of citizenship education aims to ensure that these programs are carried out as effectively and efficiently as possible and that the objective of fostering national character is met. (Adiansyah & Widiatmaka, 2022). Theoretically the civic education course has been very effective in building the nation's character, but in implementation it has not shown optimal results because many students do not yet have civic competencies. Many students still commit acts that are against the law or not in accordance with the nation's personality, such as drugs, sexual harassment and so on.

The role shown by civics education in tertiary institutions is considered to be less than optimal in anticipating the negative impacts of globalisation. The lack of duration of civics might influence it, only 16 meetings for 2 credits (50 minutes/meeting), including midterm and final semester exams (Bahrudin, 2019). Additionally, using less-than-ideal lecturing techniques and media is a barrier to citizenship education. We are currently in the era of society 5.0, which emphasises the use of digital technology, but lecturers continue to use traditional learning techniques and do not make use of digital-based learning. Given that students belong to a generation that cannot be isolated from digital technology, this declines students' learning motivation (Rahman et al., 2019). According to Law No. 14 of 2005 concerning Teachers and Lecturers, a lecturer must master several competencies, namely pedagogic, professional, personality and social, but many lecturers whose pedagogical competence is lacking so that the learning methods are less varied.

Students' interest in the culture of other countries is higher than that of the Indonesian nation's culture, even though it contains values that conflict with the nation's personality (Suhardiyansyah et al., 2016). College students are a digital native who are always driven to keep up with the times, especially lifestyle and fashion. Through their cell phones, they can have references from other countries. It might be without any filter, whether it is against the nation values or not, such as how to dress properly, individualism and so forth (Nuryadi & Widiatmaka, 2022). Another example is during online learning through Zoom meetings OR Google meetings, many students do not pay attention to the material presented by the lecturer. In the discussion process, students remain silent when asked or allowed to respond to an opinion (Tutuarima et al., 2022).

Undeniably, many students engage in behavior inconsistent with Pancasila values, even going so far as to conduct illegal activities. The challenges cause these behaviors that civic education faced, which ultimately have consequences for students' failure to develop national character. Like a ticking time bomb for Indonesian education, the government officials and higher education administrators need to take prompt action to address this issue so that this risk can be anticipated. Civics education as a required subject in higher institutions must be aligned with the more dynamic nature of times, mainly digital technologies.

CONCLUSION

Building national character is one of the main goals of education in Indonesia, especially civics education courses, bearing in mind that many actions taken by students are inconsistent with Pancasila values and thus against the law in Indonesia. The role of civics education as a compulsory subject in tertiary institutions is to build civics knowledge, citizenship skills and civic attitudes or character in students. Still, national character is the primary goal of civics education, considering that national education aims to build student character. Theoretically, civics education is very effective for building national character in students, but it is still far from expectations when viewed from its application. The output of character development is not optimal, and many students, as digital natives, take actions or behave, contradicting the Pancasila values due to the several obstacles of civic education. It includes the lack of learning hours and the low lecturers' competencies. Many students are also more interested in foreign cultures than their own. Moreover, low motivation, especially during online learning, is another negative factor.

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